

PROCEDURE FOR THE IDENTIFICATION AND MONITORING OF GROUND DEFORMATIONS THROUGH SATELLITE DATA IN UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE SITES

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Nowadays, ensuring the safeguard of natural, cultural and mixed UNESCO sites is increasingly difficult, due to not only ravages of time or anthropic actions but also to natural events. Even though it is widely recognized that UNESCO World Heritage Sites are threatened by geological risks, the level of attention placed on geohazards appears to be poor, especially if compared with the others potential threatening factors, such as wars, uncontrolled urban development or arsons.

Promoting the detection and monitoring of geohazards should become a common practice, in order to preserve the Outstanding Universal Value of UNESCO properties over time.

This study, therefore, shows a new satellite data analysis procedure to identify, in a fast, simple and repeatable way, the temporal and spatial evolution of the most critical and reliable ground deformation areas related to slow-kinematic geohazards (volcanic activity, slow-moving landslides or ground-subsidence). This approach has been tested in the Tuscan UNESCO sites (Central Italy). Thanks to the main characteristics of the recent Sentinel-1 data (short revisit time, systematic and free availability for all data users and worldwide coverage), this procedure can be easily exploited by the local risk management decision makers of each World Heritage Site, in order to define long-term geohazards monitoring activities and conservation strategies.